

Micro-optofluidic devices for drug release characterisation in simulated, dynamic oral microenvironment

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Background and Objectives

In the evaluation of medical devices, there is a **great gap between *in vitro* testing and animal models**. In the first case we have an ideal and perfectly controlled, sterile environment and steady state conditions. On the other hand, during animal trials, we have a dynamic environment with continuous risk of bacterial infection and interactions between different tissues.

Motivated by this, our long term objective is the development of an optofluidic device for the effective **evaluation of medical devices *in vitro***. With this we should:

- Replicate the **changes of pH and temperature** found in oral cavity
- Run **long term** cell experiments
- Investigate the **interactions of different cell types**
- Perform **real time spectroscopic** measurements

Methodology

The first stage of our research, includes the initial design and evaluation of an optofluidic system for the characterisation of drug release from a chitosan scaffold.

- Computational Fluid Dynamics software (ANSYS Fluent) was utilised for simulating the flow and identifying the appropriate geometrical characteristics.
- A stereolithography 3D printer was used for the fabrication of the microfluidic device.
- UV-VIS characterisation of doxycycline
- Chitosan scaffolds – fabricated via freeze drying
- Flow cell + spectrometers for real time measurements

Results and discussion

CFD Results and Design

Utilisation of commercial CFD software (Ansys Fluent) the mixing section geometry was optimised to achieve a **homogenous solution**, by increasing **advective convection**, over a wide range of fluid ratios, showing a **range of pH's** to be achieved **dynamically**.

Figure 2). Microfluidic wireframe CAD design

The CAD design is shown in Fig. 2 The CAD model was imported to a resin-based 3D printer for fabrication.

The Experimental setup is presented in Fig. 3, consisting of mixing sections 1&2, drug release section and drug concentration measurement section.

Experimental setup and materials

Fig.4). a). CAD model of "cup" sample holder. b). Microscope image of 10mg/ml doxycycline-loaded, freeze dried 3% w/v medium molecular weight chitosan

Doxycycline loaded medium molecular weight chitosan was prepared as an example biomaterial;

- 3% w/v medium molecular weight chitosan
- 2% v/v acetic acid
- 98% v/v de-ionised water
- 10,000 ppm doxycycline

The sample **volume of 10 µL** were extruded into the "cup" sample holder, shown in Fig. 4. Samples were **frozen and lyophilized** over one-day periods. The samples were then loaded onto the micro-optofluidic device through **screw-and thread**. A **rubber O-ring** was used to provide a **seal**.

Doxycycline release profiles

The drug release profile from the chitosan were calculated based on the measured UV-vis absorption at **276 nm** and **347 nm**. A drug release recorded over a **5000 second period**, under a flow rate of **13.125 mL · hr⁻¹** (stimulated) **pH of 6.5 and 5.5 at 20°C**. Also the drug release at a flow rate of **0.563 mL · hr⁻¹** (unstimulated) and **pH of 6.5 and 5.5 at 20°C** [1] [2]."

The **minimum drug concentration** able to be measured was **1 ppm**. No drug release is measured within 120 s and 0.5 h due to the residence time of the device.

Conclusions

This work demonstrates the successful:

- **Design, simulation and optimisation** of an initial micro-optofluidic device where different oral conditions can be replicated.
- **Incorporation of UV-Vis spectroscopic components that allow that allows measuring a minimum concentration of 1 ppm of drug.**
- **Average drug release increased by a factor of 1.5-2.0 for pH 5.5 and 2.0-3.0 for unstimulated conditions**

Future work

- Evaluation of drug release at different pH values and comparison to HPLC
- Incorporation of in-line real-time FTIR
- Characterisation of additional material and measurement
- Measurement of release from different biomaterials and concentrations
- Measurement of release from varying the mould i.e. use porous structures

References

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- [2] J Pytko-Polonczyk, J. et al. (2017). Artificial saliva and its use in biological experiments. *Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology: An Official Journal of the Polish Physiological Society*, 68(6), pp.807-813.

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